

CFD MODELLING OF THE URBAN MICROCLIMATE: THE CASE OF AN UNIVERSITY CAMPUS IN PORTUGAL

DIOGO NASCIMENTO¹, ANA MIRANDA², FERNANDO GUIOMAR³, VERA RODRIGUES⁴

¹ CESAM - Centre for Environmental and Marine Studies & Department of Environment and Planning, University of Aveiro, diogo.nascimento@ua.pt

² CESAM - Centre for Environmental and Marine Studies & Department of Environment and Planning, University of Aveiro, miranda@ua.pt

³ IT – Instituto de Telecomunicações, Aveiro, guiomar@av.it.pt

⁴ CESAM - Centre for Environmental and Marine Studies & Department of Environment and Planning, University of Aveiro, vera.rodrigues@ua.pt

Keywords: Urban areas, Atmospheric Boundary Layer, OpenFOAM, Urban heat.

The use of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) for modelling the atmospheric boundary layer and the urban microclimate has been experiencing advances in the last decade [1]–[4]. Also, with the advancements in computational power, the capacity to accurately model more complex urban scenarios is demonstrated in multiple studies covering a wide range of subjects including urban atmospheric flows and microclimate [5], [6], urban air quality, as well as other atmosphere-structure interactions such as building energy demand [7] and wind energy applications [8], [9]. This progress is significantly expanding our capacity to analyse and understand urban environments.

This work aims to assess average wind speeds and temperatures around part of the University of Aveiro (UA) campus. A computational domain of 2200 m x 2200 m x 240 m and divided into (20 m x 20 m) hexahedral cells was generated (Figure 1), vertical stretching was imposed. A central circular area of interest, with 1000 m diameter was defined for further levels of refinement. The total number of mesh cells is 7 148 725. The design of the computational domain followed a set of best practices [10]. CFD simulations were performed with OpenFOAM 2212 using an Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes approach with a realizable k - ϵ turbulence model. Inlet boundary conditions for the atmospheric boundary layer were derived from data collected over an entire day during a summer heatwave. Boundaries have an inlet-outlet condition that follows

Figure 1: Computational Domain

vertical wind and turbulence profiles according to the equations 1, 2 and 3. The aerodynamic roughness length (Z_0) of surrounding area was classified according to the Davenport classification.

$$u = \frac{u^*}{\kappa} \ln \left(\frac{z - d + z_0}{z_0} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$k = \frac{(u^*)^2}{\sqrt{C_\mu}} \sqrt{C_1 \ln \left(\frac{z - d + z_0}{z_0} \right) + C_2} \quad (2)$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{(u^*)^3}{k(z - d + z_0)} \sqrt{C_1 \ln \left(\frac{z - d + z_0}{z_0} \right) + C_2} \quad (3)$$

Where: u = wind speed [ms^{-1}]; u^* = friction velocity [ms^{-1}]; k = turbulent kinetic energy (TKE) [m^2s^{-2}]; z = ground-normal coordinate [m]; z_0 = aerodynamic roughness length [m]; d = ground-normal displacement height [m]; C_μ = empirical constant; κ = von Kármán constant; C_1 and C_2 = Curve-fitting coefficients. The simulation results reveal an average wind speed of 4.7 ms^{-1} across the computational domain. However, within the campus at a height of $z = 1.5 \text{ m}$, several locations experience lower wind speeds ($< 1.5 \text{ ms}^{-1}$) as illustrated in Figure 2. This occurs mainly due to vortex generation in building corners and barrier effect. It is worth noting that local temperature patterns are significantly influenced by both wind speed and wind direction. The average temperature was $27.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with local variations ranging from $27.3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $27.8 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Figure 2 further demonstrates the presence of warmer areas near the southern buildings and cooler spots near the northern campus buildings.

These results are of high relevance to assess pedestrian wind and thermal discomfort and provide valuable insight in improving the UA campus environment and the overall comfort of its occupants.

Figure 2: Simulation results for the UA Campus. Full-day averaged wind speeds (right) and temperatures (left) at pedestrian height ($z=1.5\text{m}$).

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the OptWire project (PTDC/EEI-TEL/2697/2021) funded by the Portuguese Science and Technology Foundation through national funds. Thanks are due to CESAM (UIDP/50017/2020+UIDB/50017/2020+LA/P/0094/2020) through national funds.

References

- [1] Y. Toparlar, B. Blocken, B. Maiheu, and G. J. F. van Heijst, “A review on the CFD analysis of urban microclimate,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 80. Elsevier Ltd, pp. 1613–1640, Dec. 01, 2017. doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2017.05.248.
- [2] N. R. M. Sakiyama, J. Frick, T. Bejat, and H. Garrecht, “Using cfd to evaluate natural ventilation through a 3d parametric modeling approach,” *Energies (Basel)*, vol. 14, no. 8, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.3390/en14082197.
- [3] V. Rodrigues *et al.*, “Adaptation to Climate Change at Local Scale: A CFD Study in Porto Urban Area,” in *Computational Fluid Dynamics - Basic Instruments and Applications in Science*, InTech, 2018. doi: 10.5772/intechopen.72972.
- [4] M. Shirzadi, P. A. Mirzaei, and M. Naghashzadegan, “Improvement of k-epsilon turbulence model for CFD simulation of atmospheric boundary layer around a high-rise building using stochastic optimization and Monte Carlo Sampling technique,” *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics*, vol. 171, pp. 366–379, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.jweia.2017.10.005.
- [5] V. Rodrigues *et al.*, “Improving the design of an open auditorium: On the relationship between flow dynamics and building arrangement,” *Sustain Cities Soc*, vol. 64, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.scs.2020.102513.
- [6] J. Allegrini, V. Dorer, and J. Carmeliet, “Influence of morphologies on the microclimate in urban neighbourhoods,” *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics*, vol. 144, pp. 108–117, Sep. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.jweia.2015.03.024.
- [7] A. Kamal *et al.*, “Impact of urban morphology on urban microclimate and building energy loads,” *Energy Build*, vol. 253, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.enbuild.2021.111499.
- [8] D. Cabezón, E. Migoya, and A. Crespo, “Comparison of turbulence models for the computational fluid dynamics simulation of wind turbine wakes in the atmospheric boundary layer,” *Wind Energy*, vol. 14, no. 7, pp. 909–921, 2011, doi: 10.1002/we.516.
- [9] B. Loganathan, M. Zaid, and H. Chowdhury, “Harvesting wind energy from the complex urban environment using CFD approach,” in *3rd International Conference on Energy and Power*, 2022. doi: 10.1063/5.0117102.
- [10] J. Franke, A. Hellsten, H. Schlünzen, and B. Carissimo, “COST Action 732: BEST PRACTICE GUIDELINE FOR THE CFD SIMULATION OF FLOWS IN THE URBAN ENVIRONMENT,” Hamburg, 2007.